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Assessment of the Impact of Security Challenges on Sustainable Childhood Education among Pre-Primary School Head Teachers in Gusau Educational Authority, Zamfara State

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Abstract

The study was carried out in Gusau Educational Authority Zamfara State to investigate assessment of security challenges on sustainable childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau Educational Authority in Zamfara State, Nigeria. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population consisted of 30 head teachers in Gusau Educational Authority, Zamfara State purposively used as the sample size of the study. A self-designed instrument titled “Assessment of Security Challenges on Sustainable Childhood Education Questionnaire (ASCSCEQ)” was used for data collection. The questionnaire was subjected to face-and content validity by experts in education from University of Nigeria, Nsukka and with a reliability estimate value of 0.85 obtained using Cronbach Alpha method. Mean and standard deviation were used for answering the research questions while t-test analysis was used in testing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed no significant difference in the opinion of the respondents on the assessment of Security challenges on childhood education and among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau Educational Authority, Zamfara state. The result also showed no significant difference in the opinion of male and female head teachers on the on the consequences of security challenges on childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau Educational Authority, Zamfara state. The study recommended among others that the people of Zamfara and especially the school head teachers should report any acts of security challenges within the state to the appropriate educational authorities.

Keywords: Assessment, Herdsmen, Insecurity, Challenges, Childhood Education

Introduction

Insecurity is one of the major problems threatening the nations' socio-economic development. The high incidence of insecurity has assumed dangerous dimensions thereby disrupting the social life of the people and hampering the educational progress of the citizens across the nations. Consequently, hardly a day passes without news of banditry, kidnapping, herdsmen activities, robbery, raping and other cyber-crimes being reported in some of the national dailies (Dantala, 2014). Presently, the nation appears to be grappling with security challenges cutting across its six geopolitical zones with the North-East, North-Central, South-South and South-East being the hottest. Residents in this area are forced to sleep with one eye open in an environment of uncertain tings while the governments charged with the responsibility of protecting the citizens seems confused and handicapped (Nwozor, 2013).

Security in a narrow sense is opposite of insecurity. Nwagboso (2012) states that security is an essential concept which is commonly associated with the alleviation of threats to the survival of individuals or groups. Consequently, according to him security can be equated with freedom from present and future danger, harm or anxiety. However, the author also argues that security may not be the absence of threats but it is the ability to respond to threats with appropriate skill and expertise. Otto and Ukpere (2012) assert that security relates to the presence of peace, safety, happiness and the protection of human and physical resources or the absence of crisis. Also, Omoyibo and Akpomira (2012) asserts that security in Nigeria synonymous to an individual who put iron bars across his or her windows which eventually prevents the individual from escaping a fire outbreak. According to the authors, the only condition for the maintenance of peace and the guarantee of security is by upholding law and order. By this, state could be secured against threats which may include low level civil disorder, crime, organized violence and even an armed insurgency (EL-rufai, 2012).

However, the current security challenges in Gusau Educational Authority of the country appear to be a thorn in the flesh in the educational development of the people of Zamfara State. Zamfara, one of the States created in 1996 out of the then Sokoto State shares common boundaries with Kastina to the East, Sokoto State to the West, Kebbi, Nija and Kaduna State to the South (International Crisis Group, 2020). The state comprises 14 Local Government Areas with a land mass of 39,762 km² and with a population of 3.3million people based on national census figure of 2006. Most of Zamfara state is savanna

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occasionally interspersed with vast forests that provides homes to thousands of most Fulani herders. The incidence of migration and violent clashes between Fulani herders and farmers in many parts of the state has made it possible for a new dimension of security threats to be common occurrence. These are armed banditry, arms trafficking, cattle rustling, illegal mining of solid minerals, smuggling as well as kidnapping for ransom among others (International Crisis Group, 2020).

Zamfara State is one the states in the North-West that is constantly being affected or terrorized by security challenges arising from the above vices. This has not only affected economic activities of the people but has become worrisome in relation to the educational progress in the state with regards to childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau Educational Authority, Zamfara state. Childhood education is the foundation of the world's future and must be given the highest priority in all ramifications. It is the right of every child to be educated, since education seems to be one of the natural occurrences associated with human growth. Early childhood education development basically deals with physical care and education of young children from birth to eight years of age. Early childhood education forms part of education in Nigeria and falls under the joint responsibility of the Ministry of Education, the Universal Basic Education Commission (UBEC), in collaboration with the Local Government Education Authority. According to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014) in her National Policy on education, Early Childhood Education is the education given in an educational institution to children prior to their entering the primary school, it includes the crèche, the nursery and the kindergarten. Early Childhood Education years set the foundation for life because it results in easier transition to primary school United Nations International Children Emergency Fund (UNICEF, 2013).

Based on the importance of Early Childhood Education to not only the nation but also to the growing child, it becomes imperative to forestall or explore security threats or challenges associated with it. This is why it becomes expedient to address the issue of the assessment of security challenges on sustainable childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau educational authority in Zamfara State in particular. This is because when people experience a difference in what they see and believe and what they desire as the gap between the rich and the poor, it widens people's information and brings about more confusion in the security situation. This is what people experience in Zamfara State. Olayoku (2014) asserts that the genesis of security challenges in Zamfara State could be attributed to the periods 2009 to 2011 but aggravated after the general election 2019. Anka (2017) observed that the incidence between the Fulani herders and the people in some parts of Zamfara State such as Dumburum in Zurmi, Badarawa in Shinkafi, Kizara in Tsafe and Dangulbi in Maru Local Government resulted to reprisal attacks that led to the death of many people in the area. According to WANEP NEW (2019) over 5,000 women were widowed, 25,000 were orphaned while more than 190,000 others were displaced.

Furthermore, the immediate cause of increase in security challenges was the activities of the Yansakai group which was born out of the banditry activities of the local people who were mostly Fulani herders. During this time, the nomads harassed people in isolated communities in many parts of Zamfara state. According to Olayokun (2014) in an attempt to checkmate the activities of the Fulanis who were harassing the local communities using cutlasses, dane guns and sticks for their operations especially in isolated villages and forest, the Yansakai or the vigilante group carried out their own operation against this Fulanis at the rural communities. In that operation in Maru LGA in Zamfara state, the vigilante group killed an ex-police officer named Samaila Yakubu and another Fulani who was set ablaze inside his pickup van. The Fulanis went and regrouped and organized themselves into different groups, acquiring dangerous weapons such as Ak47, double- and single-barrel guns, dane guns and general-purpose machine guns and planned reprisal attack on the people. This attack resulted to so many casualties including damage to farms educational institutions and other social activities in Zamfara state.

The above not only disrupted socio-economic activities of the people but also truncated the educational progress especially childhood education seen as a basis for the foundation of the educational future for the security of the nation and sustainable development. It could be noted that there is no village in Zamfara State that has not witnessed the impact of armed banditry. Rufai (2018) observes that in Mada district in Gusau Local Government Area, over 12 different attacks by bandits claim the life of over 20 people and 1,500 cattle stolen at different times from 2014-2016. This has naturally hindered childhood and other forms of educational activities of the people of Zamfara State. Consequently, these security challenges are common occurrence in almost all the villages in the state. Against this backdrop, this study seeks to examine and also investigate the assessment of security challenges on sustainable childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau educational authority in Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the impact of security challenges on sustainable childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau educational authority in Zamfara State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

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1. Examine the nature of security challenges on childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau Educational Authority in Zamfara State
2. Assess the impact of security challenges on childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau Educational Authority, Zamfara state

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study

1. What is the nature of security challenges on childhood education in Zamfara Sate?
2. What are the impacts of security challenges on childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau Educational Authority, Zamfara state?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses will guide the study and will be tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant difference between male and female head teachers in Zamfara state LGEA, in Zamfara Sate on the nature of the assessment of security challenges on sustainable childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau educational authority in Zamfara State
2. There is no significant difference between male and female Head teachers on the consequences of security challenges on childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau Educational Authority, Zamfara state

Methodology

The study was carried out in Zamfara state to determine the assessment of security challenges on sustainable childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau educational authority in Zamfara State, Nigeria. Two research questions and two null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance guided the study. The study adopted a cross sectional survey research design. The population comprised of 30 head teachers 30 public childhood centers in Zamfara Local Government Education Authority purposively sampled and used as the sample size of the study. A researcher-designed questionnaire titled Assessment of Security Challenges on Sustainable Childhood Education among Pre-Primary School Head Teachers Questionnaire (ASCSCPHQ) was used as instrument for data collection. The questionnaire was validated by three experts in the Department of Educational Foundations, two from Sociology Unit and one from Measurement and Evaluation, all in University of Nigeria, Nsukka. it has an overall reliability estimate of 0.85 obtained using Cronbach Alpha method. The instrument was structured on a 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree(SD) with assigned values of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions while t- test analysis was used in testing the hypotheses at 0.05 levels of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the nature of security challenges on childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau Educational Authority, Zamfara state?

Table 1 Mean ratings of Head teachers on the nature of security challenges on childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau Educational Authority, Zamfara state.

S/N	Item Statement	X	SD	Dec
1	Childhood centers are closed down for security reasons	3.03	0.70	Agree
2	School structures are destroyed by bandits	3.16	0.62	Agree
3	Families are displaced from their homes	3.20	0.60	Agree
4	Some teachers are kidnapped by unknown persons	3.14	0.63	Agree
5	Many school records are destroyed	3.30	0.56	Agree
6	Some schools are set ablaze by Fulani herdsmen	3.22	0.61	Agree
7	Learning facilities are burnt by herdsmen	3.25	0.65	Agree
8	School calendars are affected	3.12	0.68	Agree
Grand mean		3.16	0.62	Agree

The result in table one shows the responses of the head teachers on the nature of security challenges on childhood education and sustainable development in Zamfara state. The mean scores of the respondents on items 1-8 are seen to be above

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the criterion mean of 2.50 benchmark for acceptance level. This implies that the respondents are in agreement that items 1-8 are the nature of security challenges on childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau Educational Authority, Zamfara state. The cluster mean and the standard deviation is an indication that the respondents' views are close to each other on the items. This grand mean supports the above result.

Research Question 2

What are the consequences of security challenges on childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau Educational Authority, Zamfara state?

Table 2 Mean ratings of Head teachers on the consequences of security challenges on childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau Educational Authority, Zamfara state

S/N	Item Statement	X	SD	Dec
9	Insecurity leads to closure of schools	3.01	0.70	Agree
10	It hampers education activities of the children	3.20	0.65	Agree
11	It leads to burning of childhood schools	3.10	0.68	Agree
12	Insecurity affects educational development of the state	3.30	0.62	Agree
13	It widens the gap of underdevelopment in education in the area	3.06	0.69	Agree
14	It leads to change of academic calendar of schools	3.24	0.64	Agree
15	It leads to abandonment of school activities	3.00	0.71	Agree
16	It leads to displacement of teachers in schools	3.14	0.63	Agree
	Grand Mean	3.10	0.68	Agree

Result in table 2 above shows that the mean scores of the head teachers on the consequences of security challenges on childhood education and sustainable development in Zamfara State are observed to be above 2.50 criterion mean for acceptance of an item on items 9-16 on the table.

This implies that the head teachers are in agreement that items 9-16 are the consequences of security challenges on childhood education and sustainable development in Zamfara State. The above result is also supported by the mean scores of the head teachers on the table.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between male and female head teachers in Zamfara state LGEA, in Zamfara State on the nature of security challenges on childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau Educational Authority, Zamfara state

Table 3: t-test analysis of male and female head teachers on the nature of security challenges on childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau Educational Authority, Zamfara state

S/N	Group	N	X	SD	df	Cal-t value	Critical-t value	Level sign	of Dec
1	Male	22	3.14	0.70	28	0.75	1.96	0.05	NS
2	Female	8	3.00	0.74					

Table 3 above shows that the calculated t-value of 0.75 is less than the critical t-value of 1.96 at 28 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. Since the t-calculated value is less than t-critical value, the null hypotheses of no significant difference of the study is accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference between male and female head teachers responses on the nature of the assessment of security challenges on sustainable childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau educational authority in Zamfara State

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between male and female Head teachers on the consequences of security challenges on childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau Educational Authority, Zamfara state

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Table 4: t-test analysis of male and female head teachers on the consequences of security challenges on childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau Educational Authority, Zamfara state

S/N	Group	N	X	SD	df	Cal-t value	Critical-t value	Level of sign	of Dec
1	Male	22	3.11	0.73	28	0.055	1.96	0.05	NS
2	Female	8	3.16	0.71					

Table 4 indicates that the calculated t-value of 0.055 is less than the critical t-value of 1.96 at 28 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. Since the t-calculated value is less than t-critical value, the second hypothesis of no significant difference of the study is accepted. This implies that both male and female Head teachers did not differ in their views on the consequences of security challenges on childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau Educational Authority, Zamfara state

Discussion of the Findings

The findings of the study identified the following as the nature of assessment of security challenges on sustainable childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau educational authority in Zamfara State. These include closing of Childhood education centers for security reasons, destruction of School structures by bandits or herdsmen, displacement of families from their homes and kidnapping of some teachers by unknown persons. Other nature of the assessment of security challenges on childhood education in the area include destruction of school records, setting some schools ablaze thereby destroying learning facilities and also affecting school academic calendars. The above findings are in agreement with the opinions of Dandala (2014) and also Tona (2012) who noted that the nature of security challenges in Zamfara state included closure of schools, destruction of school records, displacement of teachers and burning of some school structures through activities of herdsmen and bandits. The above nature of the assessment of security challenges on sustainable childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau educational authority in Zamfara State was supported by the hypothesis of no significant difference of the study which was accepted implying no difference in the opinions of male and female head teachers in Zamfara state.

Furthermore, the findings of the study also indicated that the consequences of the assessment of security challenges on sustainable childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau educational authority in Zamfara State, include; closure of schools, hampering of educational activities of the children, burning of schools and affecting educational development of the state. Other consequences of the assessment of security challenges on sustainable childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau educational authority in Zamfara State are widening the gap of underdevelopment in education in the area, changing of academic calendar of schools, abandonment of school activities and displacement of teachers in schools. The above findings are in agreement with the view of Ozoh and Dinwobi(2018) and Rufai(2018) who opined that security challenges in many parts of the country have affected not only economic activities but also untold damages to educational development at all levels. Furthermore, Anka (2017) observed that insecurity in many parts of Zamfara state has brought about further under development of the people educationally. This finding was equally supported by the acceptance of the hypothesis of no significant difference in the opinions of the male and female head teacher in Zamfara state.

Conclusion

It is concluded from the findings of the study that the nature of the assessment of impacts of security challenges on sustainable childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau educational authority in Zamfara State, and the consequences requires serious governmental intervention since they remain serious security challenges to childhood education in the area among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau Educational Authority, Zamfara state.

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Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The people of Zamfara and especially the school head teachers should report any acts of security challenges within the state to the appropriate educational authorities and the government for immediate attention.
2. The government and people of Zamfara are to join hands or partner with each other in finding lasting solutions to the security challenges in many parts of the state which are undermining childhood education among pre-primary school head teachers in Gusau Educational Authority, Zamfara state.

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